

Evaluation of a pilot system coupling thermal and ultrasound pretreatment, anaerobic digestion and hydrothermal carbonization for sewage sludge treatment and *per*- and polyfluoroalkyl substances removal

Evdokia Gkalipidou^a, Asimina Koukoura^a, Ioanna Savvanidou^a, Marios G. Kostakis^b,
Dimitrios Triantafyllos Gerokonstantis^b, Petros Mastoras^a, Georgia Gatidou^a,
Michail S. Fountoulakis^{a,c}, Stergios Vakalis^{a,d}, Olga S. Arvaniti^e, Nikolaos S. Thomaidis^b,
Olga-Ioanna Kalantzi^a, Athanasios S. Stasinakis^{a,*}

^a Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, Mytilene, 81100, Greece

^b Department of Chemistry, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, 15771, Greece

^c School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Greece

^d School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Greece

^e Department of Agricultural Development, Agrofood and Management of Natural Resources, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Psachna, 34400, Greece

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ABSTRACT

The presence of *per*- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in sewage sludge underscores the need to develop effective methods for their removal. As part of the ZeroPM EU project, we constructed and operated for 11 months a pilot-scale system coupling sludge pretreatment, anaerobic digestion and hydrothermal carbonization. Thermal or ultrasound pretreatment led to a significant increase in biogas production from $16 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$ to $27 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$ and $26 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$, respectively. Calculations of energy consumption showed that heating of the bioreactor accounted for the largest fraction of total energy use, ranging up to 56%, while hydrothermal carbonization contributed by 27%. The application of a fully validated analytical method in the dissolved and particulate phase of raw sludge showed that 25 out of 27 monitored PFAS were detected, and the highest total concentrations were found for 6:2FTS ($258.8 \pm 34.4 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$), PFDA ($208.1 \pm 10.7 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$), and PFOS ($155.8 \pm 27.0 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$). Sludge pretreatment did not affect the total concentrations of PFAS but slightly increased the

Abbreviations and acronyms: PFAS, Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances; STPs, sewage treatment plants; EPA, environmental protection agency; AD, Anaerobic digestion; HTC, Hydrothermal carbonization; LC-MS/MS, Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry; ACN, Acetonitrile; SPE, Solid-phase extraction; TH, Thermal; US, Ultrasound; CSTR, Continuously stirred tank reactor; SCADA, Supervisory control and data acquisition; UASB, Up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket; HRT, Hydraulic retention time; TS, Total solids; tCOD, Volatile solids, VS, Total chemical oxygen demand; sCOD, Soluble chemical oxygen demand; BOD₅, Biological oxygen demand; NH₄⁺-N, Ammonium nitrogen; PO₄³⁻-P, Orthophosphate phosphorus; SO₄²⁻, Sulfate; VFAs, Volatile fatty acids; EC, Electrical conductivity; T, Temperature; GC, Gas chromatography; UPLC, Ultra-performance liquid chromatography; EURL-POPs, European Union Reference Laboratory for Halogenated Persistent Organic Pollutants in Feed and Food; LOD, Limit of detection; LOQ, Limit of quantification; SD, Standard deviation; ME, Matrix effect; SMY, Specific methane yield; THP, Thermal pretreatment; MRM, Multiple reaction monitoring; E_v, Volumetric energy; CHP, Combined heat and power; SE, Specific energy input; FTOHs, Fluorotelomer alcohols; PFCAs, Perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids; PFSAs, Perfluoroalkyl sulfonic acids; FASAs, Perfluoroalkyl sulfonamides; FASAA, Perfluoroalkyl sulfonamido acetic acids; FTSA, Fluorotelomer sulphonic acids; PFECAs, Perfluoroether carboxylic acids; PFBA, Perfluorobutanoic acid; PFPeA, Perfluoropentanoic acid; PFHxA, Perfluorohexanoic acid; PFHpA, Perfluoroheptanoic acid; PFOA, Perfluorooctanoic acid; PFNA, Perfluorononanoic acid; PFDA, Perfluorodecanoic acid; PFUDA, Perfluoroundecanoic acid; PFDoA, Perfluorododecanoic acid; PFTrDA, Perfluorotridecanoic acid; PFTeDA, Perfluorotetradecanoic acid; PFBS, Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid; PFPeS, Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid; PFHxS, Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid; PFHpS, Perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid; PFOS, Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; PFNS, Perfluoronanesulfonic acid; PFDS, Perfluorodecanesulfonic acid; PFOSA, Perfluorooctane sulfonamide; PFOSAA, Perfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid; N-MeFOSAA, N-Methylperfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid; N-EtFOSAA, N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid; 4:2 FTS, 1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid; 6:2 FTS, 1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; 8:2 FTS, 1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorodecanesulfonic acid; ADONA, 3H-Perfluoro-3-[3-methoxy-propoxy] propanoic acid; GenX, Hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid; M2PFOA, Perfluoro-1-[1,2-¹³C₂] octanoic acid; M4PFOS, Perfluoro-1-[1,2,3,4-¹³C₄] octanesulfonic acid; M8PFOSA, Perfluoro-1-[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-¹³C₈] octanesulfonamide; LSE, Liquid-solid extraction; UD_o, Ultrasound dose; UD, Ultrasound density; OLR, Organic loading rate.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: astas@env.aegean.gr (A.S. Stasinakis).

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presence of some analytes in the dissolved fraction. No PFAS removal was observed during anaerobic digestion whereas the majority of the PFAS were removed, to a significant extent, during hydrothermal carbonization. The removal rate varied depending on the target substance and the class of PFAS. The highest removal was achieved for perfluoroalkyl sulfonamides, exceeding 95%, while the removal of perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids and perfluoroalkyl sulfonic acids ranged from 40% to 100%, and 56% to 100%, respectively.

1. Introduction

Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have been used extensively since the 1950s. Due to their unique chemical properties and environmental persistence, they are often detected in the environment and food at concerning high concentrations [1,2]. Conventional sewage treatment plants (STPs) serve as major pathways for the release of PFAS into the environment, as their tendency to sorb onto suspended solids leads to accumulation in sewage sludge at concentrations ranging up to several $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry weight [3,4]. On the other hand, almost 35% of the sewage sludge produced in EU-27 is used in agriculture, while this practise is also very common in USA and Australia [5]. So far, no limit values have been set for PFAS in sewage sludge disposed to the soil by the EU-27. However, some Nordic countries have introduced national limit values for PFOS (Sweden: 0.05 mg/kg dry weight, Norway: 0.1 mg/kg dry weight) or for the sum of 4 PFAS (Denmark: 0.01 mg/kg dry weight) [6]. Additionally, in January 2025, the EPA released a draft risk assessment reporting that, under certain conditions and scenarios, concentrations of 1 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ PFOS or PFOA in biosolids could pose risks to human health following land application of sewage sludge [7].

Among different treatment technologies used for sewage sludge treatment, anaerobic digestion (AD) is widely applied for stabilization of sludge and production of biogas. Besides the frequent detection of PFAS in sewage sludge, their removal efficiency and distribution between different phases during AD is not clear yet [4,5]. In a systematic study examining the removal of thirteen PFAS in different full-scale anaerobic digesters, Lakshminarasimman et al. [8] reported a moderate decrease of Σ -PFAS (expressed as fluorine equivalents) in three out of five bioreactors, while no clear trend was noticed for specific PFAS. Ozelcaglayan et al. [9] calculated the masses of fifteen PFAS during different sludge treatment processes in two STPs and reported -for most of them- an increase of their mass after AD. On the other hand, the masses of three PFAS precursors (FOSA, MeFOSAA, and EtFOSAA) decreased. Continuous-flow lab experiments with seven PFAS conducted under mesophilic [10] or thermophilic conditions [11] showed no removal during conventional AD while the application of ultrasound or thermal pretreatment slightly altered the distribution of longer perfluorocarboxylic acids and PFOS in sewage sludge [10].

In parallel to the above, the widespread contamination of PFAS, along with rising regulatory pressure, is driving the demand for effective PFAS treatment technologies. In a recent review, Hakeem et al. [12] summarized the most promising thermal technologies for PFAS removal from biosolids. Among them, hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is an efficient thermochemical process for treating high-moisture materials such as sewage sludge. During HTC, residual organic matter is transformed into a solid carbon-rich product and a liquid phase, in which the more volatile and oxygenated compounds are concentrated. The process is typically carried out at temperatures between 180 and 300 °C, with pressures maintained between 10 and 80 bar to keep water in its liquid state, and reaction time between 20 and 240 min [13]. So far, there is a limited number of studies investigating PFAS removal during HTC of sewage sludge and all of them have been conducted under laboratory conditions. Additionally, the combination of AD and HTC for PFAS removal from sewage sludge has not been investigated. Specifically, in a recent study, Miserli et al. [14] used sewage sludge spiked with a PFAS mixture of 15 compounds at concentrations between 10 and 200 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ and reported that the Σ PFAS removal ranged between 86.9 and 95.7%

(T: 200 °C, contact time: 180 min). Experiments from our research team at different temperatures (200–300 °C) and contact time of 120 min showed that C5–C10 perfluorocarboxylates were removed by over 94% under all tested conditions while analysis in the gas phase and mass balance calculations showed that a minor part (<0.001%) of studied PFAS was transferred to the gas phase [15].

To address key knowledge gaps regarding the fate of PFAS during sludge treatment and to evaluate the performance and novelty of an integrated treatment strategy, we designed, constructed, and operated a pilot-scale system combining AD and HTC in series. Experiments were conducted over three experimental phases. In Phase A, raw secondary sludge was used as feed of the anaerobic digester while thermal and ultrasound sludge pretreatment was applied in Phases B and C, respectively. In parallel, different temperature and pressure conditions were applied to the hydrothermal bioreactor. The system was monitored for the removal of conventional pollutants and the occurrence of 27 PFAS using a LC-MS/MS method, that was fully validated. In parallel, the production of biogas, the methane content and the energy consumption of the system was measured. The system was continuously monitored over an eleven-month period, within the framework of the Horizon 2020 ZeroPM project (<https://zeropm.eu>). This integrated approach enables the evaluation of the combined AD–HTC system performance, including a detailed assessment of overall energy consumption, as well as a systematic investigation of PFAS partitioning between the particulate and liquid phases of different processes. It is worth mentioning that the coupling of AD and HTC is of scientific interest as it combines complementary biological and thermochemical pathways, allowing sequential valorisation of sewage sludge through biogas production and conversion of residual solids into a carbon-rich, more stable material. Additionally, this study includes one of the most comprehensive targeted PFAS datasets reported for HTC to date, with a substantially larger number of compounds monitored than in most previous studies. To the best of our knowledge, only one recent lab-scale investigation has reported a slightly higher number of PFAS [16].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Stock solutions of native PFAS standards were initially prepared in methanol (MeOH) at concentrations of 1000 mg L^{-1} and were purchased from Alfa Aesar (Germany) ($\geq 95\%$). M4PFOS, M2PFOA and M8PFOSA were used as internal or surrogate standards and were supplied by Wellington Laboratories (Canada). Methanol and acetonitrile (ACN) for LC-MS were purchased from Merck (Germany). Oasis HLB solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridges (200 mg, 6 mL) were supplied by Waters™ (Milford, MA, USA). Paper filters (5–13 μm) and RC syringe filters (0.2 μm) were sourced from LLG (Germany) and Macherey-Nagel (Germany), respectively. Acetic acid (99.7%) and ultra-pure hydrochloric acid (32%) were also supplied by Merck (Germany). Ultra-pure water was produced in the laboratory using a Milli-Q/Milli-RO purification system.

2.2. Description of the pilot system

A pilot-scale system (Fig. 1a) was installed at the STP in Mytilene (Lesvos Island, Greece) to investigate the fate of PFAS during sewage sludge treatment. The system included in series a thermal (TH) or ultrasound (US) pretreatment step, an AD bioreactor, and an HTC reactor.

The thermal pretreatment unit comprised a sealed stainless-steel vessel (AISI 304) with a total volume of 30 L, in which secondary sewage sludge was heated using an electric resistance heater over a temperature range of 30 to 110 °C. A Hielscher UIP1000hdT (Teltow, Germany) ultrasound sonicator with a maximum output power of 1000 W and an operating frequency of 20 kHz was used for ultrasound pretreatment. The main parameters and operating conditions of the US pretreatment are summarized in Table S1 of the supplementary material. The AD reactor was constructed from stainless-steel (AISI 304) with a total volume of 500 L, equipped with an agitator of 2740 rpm. It was designed as a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) with a double-wall jacket for hot-water recirculation, heated by a boiler, while it was externally insulated with 40 mm of thermal insulation to minimize heat loss. A high-pressure 8 L Parr 4550 (Moline, IL, USA) HTC reactor equipped with reactor controller 4848B was used to regulate pressure and motor speed, as well as to enable real-time monitoring. The reactor had a rated maximum pressure of 130 bar and a maximum operating temperature of 350 °C. The pilot system was monitored and controlled via a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, which provided remote control of key process parameters, alarm management, historical data logging, and user interface for operational monitoring and process optimization. A Shelly Pro 3EM three-phase energy meter was installed in the pilot system's electrical panel to monitor and calculate the energy consumption of the pilot unit.

2.3. Experimental procedure

The pilot system operated for a period of eleven months (June 2024–April 2025) treating 28 L of secondary sewage sludge per day. For the start-up of the AD reactor, anaerobic sludge from an up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor was used as inoculum [17]. The acclimatization period lasted 60 days (June 2024 – July 2024) to ensure stable microbial activity and consistent process conditions. To investigate the fate of PFAS and the impact of sludge pretreatment on the performance of AD, three experimental phases were conducted. In Phase A, the operation of the AD in combination with HTC was monitored for 77 days (August 2024–October 2024). In Phase B, the TH pretreatment process (80 °C, 1 h) was evaluated in combination with AD and HTC over a 40-day period (November 2024–December 2024) while in Phase C, the US pretreatment process (20 kHz, 900 W, 15 min) was monitored alongside with AD and HTC for 53 days (February 2025–April 2025). Throughout the entire experiment, the AD operated under mesophilic conditions at 37 °C, with a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 18 days. As regards the operation of HTC reactor, in Phases A and B, it operated at 200 °C and 17 bar pressure (2 h contact time) while in Phase

C at 250 °C, 36 bar pressure (2 h contact time).

For evaluating the performance of the pilot system, influent and effluent samples were collected from each unit twice a week to monitor its performance in terms of total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS), total (tCOD) and soluble (sCOD) chemical oxygen demand, biological oxygen demand (BOD₅), ammonium nitrogen (NH₄⁺-N), orthophosphate phosphorus (PO₄³⁻-P), sulfate (SO₄²⁻), volatile fatty acids (VFAs), alkalinity, pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and temperature (T). In parallel, measurements of the produced biogas flow rate (L d⁻¹), as well as the composition of the biogas at the outlet of the CSTR, were conducted. For the determination of PFAS in the inlet and outlet of each unit, samples were also taken during four consecutive days in Phases A and B, and five days in Phase C. The sampling points are shown in Fig. 1b.

2.4. Analytical methods

2.4.1. Conventional pollutants and environmental parameters

BOD₅ analysis was performed using the respirometric method, SO₄²⁻ was measured photometrically using the appropriate HACH reagent (SulfaVer 4, Method 8051), TS, VS, COD, NH₄⁺-N, PO₄³⁻-P and alkalinity were measured according to Standard Methods [18]. The pH, T and conductivity were monitored with a portable multimeter (WTW MULTI 3630 IDS) while a portable gas analyzer (BIOGAS 5000 Geotech) was used to determine the composition of the produced biogas. The determination of VFAs (acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid, isobutyric acid, valeric acid and isovaleric acid) was conducted using an Agilent 6890 N GC with a flame ionization detector, as described by Gkalipidou et al. [10].

2.4.2. PFAS analysis and validation of the method

Twenty-seven (27) PFAS compounds belonging to six (6) different classes were analysed in both the dissolved and solid phases of sewage sludge and hydrochar samples (Table S2, following the modified method described by Arvaniti et al. [19]. Immediately after sampling, samples were centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 15 min. The liquid fraction was filtered using filter paper (47 mm LLG-Filter papers, LLG-Labware, Germany) and membrane (0.45 µm; Whatman, Germany), while the solid fraction was dried at 40 °C for one day (raw, pretreated and anaerobically digested sludge) or 2–3 days for hydrochar. All samples were stored at –20 °C until extraction and analysis. As regards samples pretreatment, Oasis HLB SPE cartridges were used to isolate PFAS from the liquid samples, while solid samples were extracted via ultrasonication using basic methanol as the extraction solvent and subsequently cleaned using the same SPE method applied to the liquid phase. A detailed description of the analytical method can be found in Section 1 of Supplementary

Fig. 1. (a) Parts of the pilot-scale sewage sludge treatment system used in the current study (left picture): (1) thermal pretreatment, (2) ultrasound pretreatment, (3) anaerobic digester, (4) hydrothermal carbonization reactor. (b) Operational conditions and sampling points (right picture): (S1) inlet, (S2) outlet of thermal pretreatment, (S3) outlet of ultrasound pretreatment, (S4) outlet of anaerobic digester and (S5) outlet of hydrothermal carbonization reactor.

Material. An UPLC system (Exion™ LC) coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometer of AB Sciex QTRAP 6500 + (AB Sciex, Canada) was used for the qualitative and quantitative determination of target compounds.

The analytical method for the determination of PFAS was validated for its linearity, detectability (limit of detection-LOD and limit of quantification-LOQ), precision, and matrix effects. For validation assessment in environmental samples, there is no specific guideline, for this reason the guidelines of EURL-POPs [20] were used for the determination of PFAS in Food and Feed. Linearity was accessed using ten concentration levels of spiked samples ranging from 0.25 to 50 µg L⁻¹ and evaluated by linear correlation coefficient (R²). Inter-day precision was assessed by analyzing 18 replicate samples on two separate days. Recovery experiments were performed at a concentration level of 10 µg L⁻¹ using nine replicates, and precision was expressed as the relative standard deviation (%RSD) calculated from the recovery results. For monitoring purposes, recoveries within the range of 65–135% were considered satisfactory. Regarding detectability, LOD and LOQ were estimated. LODs and LOQs were defined as 3.3 × SD/b and 3 × LOD, respectively, where SD was the standard deviation of the response of nine replicates of 0.50 µg L⁻¹ PFAS mixture and b was the slope of the spiked calibration curve. For the calculation of average concentrations, PFAS with values between LOD and LOQ were replaced by LOQ/2 [21], while individual PFAS with values below LOD were replaced with LOD/2. To assess the extent to which the experimental results represent the true analyte concentrations in real sample matrices, the matrix effect (ME) was evaluated by post-extraction spiking of analytes into the extracts of all four matrices and calculated as [(Ratio Matrix Match-Ratio Blank Matrix)/(Ratio Standard)] × 100. Ratio is defined as the ratio of the area of the analyte to the area of the internal standard.

2.5. Equations and statistical analysis

The removal efficiency of major pollutants in different parts of the pilot system was calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = \frac{C_{in} - C_{out}}{C_{in}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, C_{in} and C_{out} correspond to influent (mg L⁻¹) and effluent (mg L⁻¹) concentrations, respectively.

The HRT was calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$\text{HRT (d)} = \frac{V}{Q} \quad (2)$$

where, V (m³) is the volume of the AD and Q (L d⁻¹) is the daily flowrate.

The organic loading rate (OLR) was calculated in terms of daily mass flow of COD, according to Eq. (3):

$$\text{OLR} \left(\frac{\text{gCOD}}{\text{m}^3 \text{d}} \right) = \frac{Q \times [\text{COD}]}{V} \quad (3)$$

where, Q (L d⁻¹) is the daily influent flowrate and [COD] (mg L⁻¹) is the concentration of COD in sewage sludge introduced to the AD reactor.

The specific methane yield (SMY) was calculated according to Eq. (4) or Eq. (5):

$$\text{SMY (Nm}l_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ gVS}_{\text{add}}) = \frac{p \times Q_{\text{biogas}}}{M_{\text{VS}}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{SMY (Nm}l_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ gCOD}_{\text{rem}}) = \frac{p \times Q_{\text{biogas}}}{M_{\text{COD}}} \quad (5)$$

where p was the methane content of biogas (%), Q_{biogas} was the produced biogas volume (Nm³ d⁻¹), M_{VS} (g d⁻¹) was the influent VS mass of the secondary sludge fed to the AD and M_{COD} (g d⁻¹) was the mass of COD removed in the AD.

A detailed description of the equations of COD mass balance, US parameters and energy consumption can be found in Section 2 of Supplementary material.

The removal of PFAS for each unit of the system was calculated using Eq. (6)

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = \frac{M_{in} - M_{out}}{M_{in}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where M_{in} is the mass of each target compound at the influent and M_{out} is the mass of each target compound at the outlet of each system's unit.

The PFAS masses (expressed as ng d⁻¹) were calculated by considering the PFAS found both in the dissolved and particulate phase (Eq. (7)):

$$M = (C_{dis} \times Q) + (C_p \times TS \times Q) \quad (7)$$

where Q is the sludge flowrate (L d⁻¹), C_{dis} is the concentration of PFAS in the dissolved phase (ng L⁻¹), C_s is the concentration of PFAS on the suspended solids (ng g⁻¹) and TS is the concentration of the total solids (g L⁻¹).

All statistical analyses were performed using OriginPro 2024 (OriginLab, USA), and p-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant. The Shapiro–Wilk test was applied to assess whether the data followed a normal distribution. The results indicated that most of the data was not normally distributed. Consequently, the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis and post-hoc Dunn's test was employed to evaluate differences in operational parameters and removal efficiencies across the experimental phases. In cases where the data met the assumption of normality, a one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test was used to assess the effect of operational variables across the four experimental phases. Different superscript letters (a, b, c, d) and asterisk (*) indicate statistically significant differences (p < 0.05).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of influent sewage sludge during different experimental phases

The characteristics of the secondary sewage sludge used as substrate for the anaerobic digester varied depending on the operational conditions of the STP and the pretreatment method applied in each Phase (Table 1). The concentrations of TS in raw sludge remained similar during Phases A (22,087 ± 2165 mg L⁻¹) and B (18,368 ± 2873 mg L⁻¹) but decreased during Phase C (13,084 ± 1708 mg L⁻¹) due to changes on the amounts of excess sludge removed from the sedimentation tank of the STP. The concentrations of sCOD, BOD₅, NH₄⁺-N and PO₄³⁻-P entering the anaerobic digester increased significantly (p < 0.05) following thermal or ultrasound pretreatment. For instance, the application of ultrasound pretreatment in Phase C increased the average concentrations of sCOD by 2111% (from 57 to 1260 mg L⁻¹), while NH₄⁺-N and PO₄³⁻-P concentrations were increased by 1000% (from 6 to 66 mg L⁻¹) and 91% (from 33 to 62 mg L⁻¹), respectively. Similarly, the application of thermal pretreatment increased the average sCOD, NH₄⁺-N and PO₄³⁻-P concentrations by 1101%, 613% and 119%, respectively. This was expected as both pretreatment processes trigger physicochemical reactions that break down microbial cell walls and release intracellular and extracellular contents into the aqueous phase [22]. A significant pH reduction was observed in the thermally and ultrasonically pretreated sludge by 0.3 and 0.2 (on average) units, respectively (Table 1). This decrease may be attributed to the formation of acidic compounds, such as VFAs, following flocs disintegration [23]. Specifically, the sum of VFAs concentration increased from 633 mg L⁻¹ in raw sewage sludge (Phase A) to 5180 mg L⁻¹ and 5710 mg L⁻¹ after thermal hydrolysis (Phase B) and ultrasonic pretreatment (Phase C), respectively (Fig. S1).

Table 1

Characteristics of the sewage sludge used in the current study and operational conditions applied in different Experimental Phases (values expressed as mean \pm sd). Values with different superscript letters (a, b) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between secondary sludge and pretreated secondary sludge in experimental phases B and C.

Parameter	Units	Phase A	Phase B			Phase C	
Duration	–	08/2024–10/2024	11/2024–12/2024			01/2025–04/2025	
Period of monitoring	days	77	40			53	
Pretreatment	–	No pretreatment	Before pretreatment	After thermal pretreatment	Before pretreatment	After ultrasound pretreatment	
Q	L d ⁻¹	28					
HRT	days	18					
pH	–	6.8 \pm 0.1	6.9 \pm 0.1 ^a	6.6 \pm 0.2 ^b	6.9 \pm 0.5 ^a	6.7 \pm 0.1 ^b	
T	°C	28.0 \pm 1.3	19.3 \pm 1.9 ^a	80 \pm 0 ^b	17.9 \pm 2.5 ^a	35.3 \pm 3.4 ^b	
Alkalinity	mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹	983 \pm 191	969 \pm 173 ^a	1092 \pm 213 ^a	518 \pm 124 ^a	520 \pm 105 ^a	
EC	mS cm ⁻¹	10.2 \pm 1.7	5.8 \pm 1.2 ^a	6.2 \pm 1 ^a	5 \pm 1.9 ^a	5.1 \pm 1.9 ^a	
TS	mg L ⁻¹	22,087 \pm 2165	18,368 \pm 2873 ^a	20,859 \pm 5793 ^a	13,084 \pm 1708 ^a	13,127 \pm 2574 ^a	
VS	mg L ⁻¹	13,703 \pm 1545	12,562 \pm 1878 ^a	14,659 \pm 4034 ^a	8927 \pm 1602 ^a	9055 \pm 2133 ^a	
tCOD	mg L ⁻¹	23,128 \pm 3644	21,352 \pm 2863 ^a	25,744 \pm 7599 ^a	17,470 \pm 1687 ^a	16,923 \pm 3537 ^a	
sCOD	mg L ⁻¹	169 \pm 97	69 \pm 36 ^a	829 \pm 141 ^b	57 \pm 17 ^a	1260 \pm 400 ^b	
BOD ₅	mg L ⁻¹	3777 \pm 557	2767 \pm 593 ^a	4313 \pm 665 ^b	1860 \pm 312 ^a	2653 \pm 550 ^b	
NH ₄ -N	mg L ⁻¹	12 \pm 8	8 \pm 9 ^a	57 \pm 17 ^b	6 \pm 4 ^a	66 \pm 31 ^b	
SO ₄	mg L ⁻¹	380 \pm 161	191 \pm 76 ^a	180 \pm 71 ^a	109 \pm 62 ^a	95 \pm 55 ^a	
PO ₄ -P	mg L ⁻¹	39 \pm 9	43 \pm 16 ^a	94 \pm 22 ^b	33 \pm 16 ^a	62 \pm 34 ^b	

3.2. Removal of conventional pollutants and production of biogas during anaerobic digestion

The removal of VS, tCOD, sCOD and total BOD₅, as well as the biogas production, were employed as indicators of anaerobic digestion performance. In Phase A, when the anaerobic digester was fed with raw secondary sludge, the removal efficiency of tCOD, BOD₅ and VS was 46 \pm 9%, 40 \pm 15% and 41 \pm 7%, respectively (Fig. S2) while formation and accumulation of scum was observed at the surface of the reactor. The concentration of sCOD at the effluent of the bioreactor was higher by 78% (Fig. 2), which can be attributed to the enzymatic and microbial hydrolysis of particulate-bound organics, leading to increased solubilization during retention in the reactor. The release of NH₄⁺-N and PO₄³⁻-P during hydrolysis of particulate organics containing nitrogen and

phosphorus was also observed, with their concentrations increasing by 750% and 100%, respectively (Fig. 2). The pH value of the anaerobic digester remained stable at 6.8 \pm 0.1 (Table 1), indicating that the available alkalinity was sufficient to maintain neutral conditions (Table S3). This suggests that the rates of VFAs production - whose dissociation release H⁺ and lowers pH- and VFA consumption by methanogens - who utilize VFAs and H⁺, thereby raising pH- were effectively balanced within the bioreactor.

In Phase B, the anaerobic reactor was fed with thermally pretreated sludge and the removal of tCOD, and VS was 30 \pm 6% and 35 \pm 4%, respectively. The application of thermal pretreatment prevented scum formation in the bioreactor, while sCOD and BOD₅ removal reached 70 \pm 8% and 61 \pm 9%, respectively (Fig. S2). The improved removal efficiency of sCOD and BOD₅ during anaerobic digestion seems to be related

Fig. 2. Influent and effluent concentration of thermal (TH), ultrasound (US) pretreatment and anaerobic digester (AD) during different experimental phases (A, B, C). tCOD concentration (a) sCOD concentration (b) PO₄-P concentration (c) NH₄-N concentration (d). Different superscript letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

to the release of easily degradable organics and the increase of their concentrations after thermal pretreatment that was reported in Section 3.1 (Table 1). As regards the prevention of scum formation, previous studies have also shown sludge pretreatment can contribute to scum reduction, thereby improving reaction kinetics and methane recovery in anaerobic digesters [24]. Although thermal pretreatment of the raw sewage sludge increased VFAs concentrations (Fig. S1), the pH in the bioreactor remained stable at 6.6 ± 0.2 . This stability indicates that the available alkalinity, primarily in the form of bicarbonate, was sufficient to buffer the system and counteract acidification resulting from VFAs accumulation. As regards the performance of the system in Phase C, the feeding of the anaerobic digester with ultrasound pretreated sludge resulted to removal efficiencies of $27 \pm 3\%$, $79 \pm 6\%$, $55 \pm 10\%$, and $36 \pm 4\%$ for tCOD, sCOD, BOD₅, and VS, respectively (Fig. S2) while the pH in the bioreactor remained stable at 6.7 ± 0.1 .

Throughout the three Phases, biogas flowrate (NL d^{-1}) and methane content (%) of the AD reactor were systematically monitored (Table 2). With the application of thermal or ultrasound pretreatment, biogas production increased significantly from $16 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$ (Phase A) to $27 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$ (Phase B) and $26 \pm 2 \text{ NL d}^{-1}$ (Phase C), respectively. This corresponds to an increase of approximately 69% in Phase B and 63% in Phase C, relative to Phase A. The enhanced biogas production in the anaerobic digester can be attributed to the elevated VFAs concentrations following sludge pretreatment, with VFAs removal efficiencies of 59% (from 5180 to 2126 mg L^{-1}) and 85% (from 5710 to 881 mg L^{-1}) observed in Phases B and C, respectively. Previous studies have also shown that the application of thermal or ultrasound pretreatment can increase the biogas production by 24–59% (after THP at 150–170 °C) [25] and 40–50% [26], respectively. Regarding methane content, it remained relatively stable across all Experimental Phases, with an average of 62%. The specific methane yield was calculated in terms of both $\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ gVS}_{\text{add}}^{-1}$ and $\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ gCOD}_{\text{rem}}^{-1}$ and the highest values were recorded in Phase C (Table 2) where the use of ultrasound pretreatment increased sCOD in the bioreactor. On the other hand, the much lower methane yield observed in Phase A can be attributed to the low fraction of biodegradable organic matter in the secondary sludge.

A COD mass balance calculation for the AD was performed considering the COD of the AD effluent, the COD equivalent of the produced gas CH_4 , the COD equivalent of dissolved CH_4 and the COD consumed by sulphate reducing bacteria, as described in Section 2 of Supplementary Material. According to the results, the average COD recovery ranged between $66 \pm 7\%$ (Phase A) and $90 \pm 8\%$ (Phase C) (Fig. S3). As regards the different fractions of COD, the COD equivalent of the produced gas CH_4 contributed to values between 5.1% (Phase A) and 9.2% (Phase B) of the total COD mass, while the COD equivalent of dissolved CH_4 had a minor contribution of COD mass balance with concentrations below 8 mg L^{-1} (<0.1%) in all experimental phases. This finding is consistent with previous reports showing that anaerobic reactors operated under

continuous mixing conditions (e.g., CSTRs) exhibit lower dissolved CH_4 concentrations compared to UASB type reactors, due to more efficient gas liquid mass transfer [27].

3.3. Performance of the hydrothermal carbonization reactor

As reported in Section 2.3, the digested sludge from AD reactor was introduced to HTC reactor for further treatment. The physicochemical characteristics of influent and effluent sludge are shown in Table S3. According to the results, a slight but statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in pH values was observed after HTC in all Phases, which can be attributed to the formation and accumulation of organic acids produced during the hydrolysis and depolymerization of organic matter under hydrothermal conditions [28]. An increase in conductivity ($p < 0.05$) was also observed, attributed to the release of ions and soluble salts into the liquid phase during HTC treatment, resulting from the breakdown of organic matter and cell lysis [29].

With regards TS and VS concentrations, reductions of 29% and 42% were observed in Phase B, and 32% and 46% (Phase C), respectively. These decreases confirm the partial solubilization of organic matter and the conversion of volatile fractions into hydrochar and dissolved compounds. The decrease was more pronounced in Phase C (250 °C, 36 bar), as high process temperatures tend to transfer more solids into the liquid fraction [30]. While tCOD values remained unchanged during HTC, the concentrations of sCOD increased significantly in all Phases ($p < 0.05$), indicating the effective solubilization of particulate organics into the liquid phase. This is in line with the hydrolytic and depolymerization reactions promoted under hydrothermal conditions, which enhance the release of soluble organics [31]. Greater COD solubilization was observed in Phases A and B (Table S3), where sCOD accounted for up to 82% of tCOD after HTC, in contrast to less than 2.4% in the AD sludge. This can be attributed to the observation that lower HTC temperatures, such as those applied in Phases A and B, favor degradation and hydrolysis processes, whereas higher temperatures promote polymerization reactions [32].

In terms of nutrients, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentrations were significantly increased after HTC, reflecting the enhanced release of organic nitrogen into the aqueous phase. The highest concentrations were observed in Phase C, a finding consistent with literature reports that elevated temperature and pressure increase ammonium concentrations in the liquid phase [33]. The solubilization of $\text{PO}_4^{3-}\text{-P}$ was favored in Phases A and B while its concentration decreased in Phase C (Table S3). It seems that the application of higher temperature and pressure led to the precipitation of orthophosphates or their densification within the hydrochar, likely forming stable, insoluble compounds [30].

3.4. PFASs analysis and occurrence in raw sludge

As regards PFAS analysis, multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions and MS parameters are presented in the Supplementary Material (Table S4). The validation of the analytical method was performed for the anaerobically digested sludge and hydrochar samples in both the dissolved and particulate phase, and the results are provided in the Supplementary Material (Tables S5–S7). For the dissolved fraction of anaerobically digested sludge samples, 24 target analytes demonstrated apparent recoveries from $86.5 \pm 11\%$ (PFHxA) to $111 \pm 14\%$ (N-EtFOSAA), while the remaining three long-chain PFCAs showed apparent recoveries of $47.7 \pm 6.2\%$ for PFTrDA, $63.8 \pm 7.6\%$ for PFTEaDA, and $65.1 \pm 5.4\%$ for PFDoA. The LODs for the same matrix were in the range of 0.17 ng L^{-1} for PFHpA to 13 ng L^{-1} for PFHxS. For the particulate fraction of the anaerobically digested sludge all target compounds demonstrated apparent recoveries in the range between $86.0 \pm 18\%$ (PFTrDA) and $107 \pm 9.1\%$ (PFPeS) while the LODs ranged between 0.50 ng g^{-1} (Adona) to 5.5 ng g^{-1} (PFDA) (Table S5). As regards hydrochar, the apparent recoveries for the dissolved fraction ranged between $52.2 \pm 5.8\%$ (PFTrDA) and 120 ± 10 (6:2 FTS) while for the

Table 2

Methane production in the anaerobic digestion reactor during different Experimental Phases (values expressed as mean \pm sd). Values with different superscript letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Parameter	Units	Phase A	Phase B	Phase C
OLR	$\text{gCOD L}_{\text{reactor}}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$	1.32 ± 0.19^a	1.16 ± 0.11^a	0.98 ± 0.10^b
				1260 ± 400^c
sCOD _{in}	mg L^{-1}	169 ± 97^a	829 ± 141^b	400^c
Biogas production	NL d^{-1}	16 ± 2^a	27 ± 2^b	26 ± 2^b
Methane production	NL d^{-1}	10 ± 1^a	17 ± 2^b	16 ± 2^b
CH_4	%	61.6 ± 6.3^a	62.3 ± 6.3^a	62.0 ± 3.6^a
Specific Methane Yield	$\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ gVS}_{\text{add}}^{-1}$	25.9 ± 4.2^a	41.6 ± 6.8^b	60.4 ± 9.4^c
Specific Methane Yield	$\text{NmL CH}_4 \text{ gCOD}_{\text{rem}}^{-1}$	46.2 ± 14.8^a	107.1 ± 26.9^b	129.8 ± 21.8^c

particulate fraction between $87.8 \pm 9\%$ (PFNS) and $114 \pm 13\%$ (PFPeA) (Table S6). The LODs were higher comparing to those of digested sludge ranging between 1.2 ng L^{-1} (PFDoA) to 31 ng L^{-1} (PFPeA) for the dissolved fraction and 0.35 ng g^{-1} for 4:2 FTS and 15 ng g^{-1} for 6:2 FTS for the particulate fraction (Table S6). For hydrochar, %RSD values ranged from 9.0% (4:2 FTS) to 20% (PFOA) in the dissolved fraction, and from 8.0% (Adona) to 20% (PFTeDA) in the particulate fraction. Most analytes showed significant signal suppression, indicating a strong matrix

effect across all four matrices (Table S7). Inter-day precision was acceptable, with all RSD values across two experimental days (18 replicates per matrix) remaining below 20%, as required by the EURL-POPs [20] guidelines.

During the different experimental phases, a total of 13 samples were collected from the system inlet and analysed to determine the occurrence of PFAS in sewage sludge. Of the 27 monitored PFAS (11 PFCAs, 7 PFSAAs, 1 FASAs, 3 FASAAAs, 3 FTSs and 2 PFECAs), PFOS and 8 PFACs

Fig. 3. Frequency of detection (a) and total concentrations (dissolved + particulate) (b) of PFAS in the influent of the pilot system ($n = 13$).

(PFPeA, PFHxA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUDa, PFDoA and PFTrDA) were detected in all raw sludge samples, two compounds (PFHpS and PFDS) were not detected in any of the samples, whereas GenX, 4:2 FTS, PFOSA, PFNS and Adona were detected only occasionally. As regards the remaining compounds, they showed detection frequencies ranging from 46% (N-EtFOSAA) to 92% (PFTeDA) (Fig. 3a). Previous studies have shown that in upstream wastewater treatment processes, FTOHs are predominantly transformed into PFCAs, which may explain why the eight previously mentioned PFCAs were detected in all raw sludge samples [8,34]. Additionally, it is widely accepted that during wastewater treatment, long-chain PFAS strongly interact with organic carbon and protein-rich materials, leading to their accumulation in the resulting sewage sludge [14].

Regarding the concentrations of PFAS in raw sludge, the highest total (dissolved + particulate) average concentration was observed for 6:2 FTS ($258.8 \pm 34.4 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$), followed by PFDA ($208.1 \pm 10.7 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$), and PFOS ($155.8 \pm 27.0 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$). Five PFCAs (PFOA, PFNA, PFHpA, PFTeDA and PFUDa) were found at concentrations in the range of 94 to 118 ng L^{-1} while the remaining PFAS were detected at lower levels (Fig. 3b). Comparison between different experimental phases shows that significantly higher concentrations ($p < 0.05$) for most analytes were observed during Phase A, while there were no differences between Phases B and C (Table S8). This could possibly be attributed to seasonal variations, as sampling for Phases B and C was carried out during the wet season (December and March, respectively), while Phase A sampling was carried out in September. These findings are supported by Tavassoli et al. [35], who observed higher PFAS concentrations in STP effluents during July, which could suggest increased PFAS precursors transformation during warmer seasons as well as higher presence of PFAS during these months.

To compare the found PFAS concentrations in raw sludge with those reported in the literature, we also expressed their values in $\text{ng g}^{-1} \text{ dw}$ (Table S9). The concentrations of individual PFAS varied among compounds while the mean total concentration in different Phases ranged from $0.04 \text{ ng g}^{-1} \text{ dw}$ (PFNS, Phase C) to $10.28 \text{ ng g}^{-1} \text{ dw}$ (6:2 FTS, Phase B). As regards PFDA, the mean concentrations in different Phases of the current study were similar to that reported in China (3.04 ng g^{-1} , [36]) and Sweden (2.5 ng g^{-1} , [37]), while higher values have been reported in Canada (15 ng g^{-1} , [8]) and Australia (15.7 ng g^{-1} , [38]). Comparable concentrations have been reported for PFOA in Sweden (1.8 ng g^{-1} ; [37]), Spain (2.85 ng g^{-1} ; [39]) and Greece (3.4 ng g^{-1} , [40]) while slightly higher have been found in Australia (8.3 ng g^{-1} [41]). Although PFOA and PFOS exhibited similar concentrations in the present study, PFOS is typically reported at higher levels in sewage sludge. For example, Navarro et al. [39] and Jiang et al. [36] reported mean PFOS concentrations of 63.99 ng g^{-1} , and 44.5 ng g^{-1} , respectively. On the other hand, Eriksson et al. [42] measured similar PFOS concentrations to those found in the present study (3 ng g^{-1}).

To the best of our knowledge this is the first study in Greece determining PFAS such as perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (FTSs), perfluoroalkanesulfonamido acetic acids (FASAs) and perfluoroalkanesulfonamides (FASAs) in sewage sludge, except for PFOSA, which was previously analysed by Miserli et al. [14]. In the current study, 6:2 FTS showed the highest mean concentration among all target PFAS in raw sludge, with a concentration of 5.14 ng g^{-1} , whereas 4:2 FTS and 8:2 FTS were either undetected or present at low levels (0.64 and 0.39 ng g^{-1} , respectively). The mean concentration of PFOSA was 1.48 ng g^{-1} , while N-EtFOSAA was measured at concentration of 1.37 ng g^{-1} . In other studies, when they included in the analysis, FTSs were consistently reported at substantially lower concentrations. On the other hand, PFSAs precursors are more commonly reported in monitoring studies. Comparable concentrations of PFOSA have been reported in the literature, with Jiang et al. [36] documenting a mean value of 1.21 ng g^{-1} and Lakshminarasimman et al. [8] reporting a median concentration of 3.3 ng g^{-1} , whereas Miserli et al. [14] observed a lower mean concentration of 0.11 ng g^{-1} .

In addition to PFAS precursors, data on the new generation PFAS compounds Adona and GenX remain very limited. In this study, Adona was rarely detected, with concentrations reaching up to 0.10 ng g^{-1} , while GenX exhibited a maximum concentration of 0.36 ng g^{-1} . Semerád et al. [43] reported concentrations of GenX ranging from 0.3 to 1.2 ng g^{-1} , whereas Gewurtz et al. [44] reported median concentrations below 1.6 ng g^{-1} for both GenX and Adona.

Investigation of PFAS distribution between the particulate and dissolved phases of the raw sludge showed that a significant proportion of these compounds was associated with suspended solids (Fig. 4). Specifically, the majority (>94%) of PFOS precursors (N-EtFOSAA, N-MeFOSAA, PFOSA and PFOA) were detected in the particulate phase, while more than 88% of 8:2 FTS, 4:2 FTS and GenX were also sorbed onto suspended solids. As regards PFCAs, the greater the number of C atoms, the higher the fraction detected in the particulate phase, ranging from 66 ± 19 for PFBA (4C atoms) to $98 \pm 1\%$ for PFTeDA (14C atoms). This finding is consistent with Arvaniti et al. [19], who reported that the sorption affinity of PFAS increases with the length of the perfluoro-carbon chain. Overall, long-chain PFAS and those containing sulfonic functional groups tend to sorb more strongly to solid fraction, however, their partitioning is also affected by cation concentration, salinity, surface charge [45], as well as by variations in wastewater chemistry and treatment processes [46]. On the other hand, it should be noted that Adona and PFNS were detected only in the dissolved fraction. For new generation PFAS such as Adona, to the best of our knowledge, no data are currently available on their partitioning behavior in sewage sludge.

3.5. Fate of PFAS during pretreatment and anaerobic digestion of sludge

No removal of PFAS from sewage sludge was observed after the application of thermal pretreatment at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in Phase B or ultrasound pretreatment at 20 kHz and 900 W in Phase C. In a previous study, Xiao et al. [47] investigated the thermal stability of PFAS on GAC and found that the decomposition of PFCAs and PFSAs requires higher temperatures, in the range of $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Additionally, Thompson et al. [48] subjected raw biosolids from full-scale facilities to laboratory thermal treatment ($115 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h) to examine changes in PFAS and their precursors and observed that concentrations of PFOA and PFOS remained unchanged. As regards ultrasonication, Campbell and Hoffmann [49] reported that the optimal frequencies for the removal of PFAS in water were 358 and 610 kHz . Zhang et al. [50] found that ultrasonication at low frequency (20 kHz), power density of 0.7 W/mL and over a period of $0\text{--}60 \text{ min}$ was ineffective in degrading PFAS in sewage sludge, while Marsh et al. [51] reported high PFAS mineralization after treating synthetic high-concentration PFAS waste solution at 700 kHz or 900 kHz . The stability of PFAS under the experimental conditions tested in this study is attributed to the high bond dissociation energy of the C—F bond ($120 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). This energy is substantially higher than that of other carbon-halogen bonds, such as 81 kcal mol^{-1} for C—Cl and 46 kcal mol^{-1} for C—Br [52]. While the pretreatment conditions applied enhanced biogas production and were beneficial for subsequent AD, they were insufficient to break C—F bonds and achieve mineralization into less toxic components such as CO_2 and fluorine.

Regarding the effects of pretreatment on PFAS distribution, it is worth mentioning that the application of thermal pretreatment significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the proportion of PFOSA and N-MeFOSAA detected in the particulate phase, while PFHpA and PFPes were entirely (100%) found in the dissolved phase (Fig. S4a). Additionally, after ultrasound pretreatment, the partitioning of two long-chain PFAS (PFOS, PFHpA) to the solid phase was also significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. S4b). These observations agree with Gkalipidou et al. [10], who found that thermal and ultrasound pretreatment of sludge increased the proportion of some long-chain PFAS in the dissolved phase, without changing their total concentrations. Moreover, Zhang et al. [50] reported the increase of PFOA, PFHpA and PFHxA in liquid fraction of sewage sludge after applying sonication for more than 15 min while

Fig. 4. Percentage of PFAS detected in the particulate phase of raw sludge across three Experimental Phases (A, B and C).

Kewalramani et al. [53] showed enhanced PFOS and PFOA desorption from contaminated soil after applying high and low frequency ultrasound treatment. Sewage sludge is embedded in a dense network of biopolymers known as extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), which govern floc stability and the retention of organic matter [24]. PFAS are known to preferentially sorb to the particulate fraction of sludge through physical interactions with organic matter and EPS. Specifically, [54] reported that hydrophobic interactions and electrostatic binding sites associated with amide and aromatic groups in proteins promote both the attraction of the fluorinated carbon chain and the carboxyl functional group of PFOA. In addition, divalent metal cations present in sludge, such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} , may act as ionic bridges between PFAS and sludge constituents [5]. According to the literature, both thermal and ultrasound pretreatment modify the EPS network of sludge. During thermal treatment this transformation is driven by hydrolysis, free radical oxidation, and sudden decompression [24], while ultrasound pretreatment similarly disrupts sludge flocs and the EPS matrix through cavitation, facilitating the desorption of organic constituents from the solid to the liquid phase [55]. Further research is required to elucidate why certain PFAS are more prone to desorption, while others remain largely associated with the solid phase.

Calculation of PFAS mass at the influents and effluents of the anaerobic bioreactor showed no PFAS removal during Experimental Phases A to C, while their concentrations were not significantly changed before and after AD. So far, the findings on PFAS biotransformation vary between studies and are not easily comparable. Li et al. [56] reported increased concentrations of PFPeA (571%), PFHxA (253%), PFBS (340%) and PFOS (91%) after aerobic digestion, while target PFAS were not removed during post-anaerobic treatment, with their concentrations either remaining unchanged or increasing in the sludge. In our previous studies, we showed in lab-scale experiments that conventional AD cannot achieve PFAS removal neither under mesophilic [10] nor thermophilic conditions [11]. In full-scale systems, Lakshminarasimman et al. [8] applied mass balances and showed 10–38% removal of Σ PFAS-F in three out of five anaerobic digesters while no removal to the other two. It is worth mentioning that the use of mass balances in anaerobic digestion reactors is complicated by the in-situ formation of PFAS from precursor compounds. For instance, Li et al. [57] demonstrated that mesophilic AD can generate perfluoroalkyl acids from precursors such as FTOHs.

3.6. PFAS fate and removal after hydrothermal carbonization

As the HTC experimental conditions were the same at Phases A and B (200 °C, 17 bar, 2 h contact time), the average PFAS removal was determined using samples collected across both phases. In the influents of the HTC reactor, 22 PFAS were detected during Phases A and B, of which 19 were removed. During Phase C, 26 PFAS were detected in the inlet, and 22 of these were removed. PFOS precursors known as FASAAs exhibited consistently high removal efficiencies, ranging from 95 ± 4% for N-MeFOSAA to 100 ± 1% for N-EtFOSAA during Phases A and B (Fig. 5a) while the increase of applied temperature in Phase C resulted to even higher removal (>99%) of these substances (Fig. 5b). Except for 4:2 FTS, the other group of studied perfluoroalkyl precursors (FTSs) showed lower removal efficiencies under both HTC conditions examined. Specifically, 6:2 FTS average removal ranged between 65 ± 2% (Phase C) and 73 ± 20% (Phases A and B), while 8:2 FTS removed by 61 ± 17% in Phase C and 74 ± 5% in Phases A and B.

PFTeDA (C14) and PFDaA (C12) exhibited the highest removals among PFCAs, with efficiencies of 94 ± 5% in Phases A/B and 99 ± 1% in Phase C, respectively. Although some PFCAs showed higher removals in Phase C, only PFHxA (C6) and PFDaA (C12) showed a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in removal after changing the HTC conditions. HTC treatment falls within the subcritical water range [58] meaning that both Phase B (200 °C, 17 bar) and Phase C (250 °C, 36 bar) maintain water in the liquid state and preserve a similar physical and chemical state of the sludge matrix. The modest increase in temperature and pressure in Phase C appears to be insufficient to further enhance most PFAS degradation indicating that a threshold had been reached. Additionally, no clear trend on their removal was observed with respect to the number of carbon atoms. On the other hand, negative removal was found for two short-chain PFAS containing carboxylic functional groups at both examined temperatures and pressures, reaching -91% for PFBA and -867% for PFPeA. This negative removal may be attributed to the transformation of PFCAs precursors or to the degradation of some long-chain PFAS into shorter-chain compounds. Similar results have also been reported in the literature for some PFAS. Miserli et al. [14] reported negative removal efficiencies for PFHpA and PFOA, while PFBA and PFTrDA were detected only in the hydrochar following HTC of sewage sludge at 180 °C for 180 min. Zhang and Liang [59] also reported that hydrothermal treatments at moderate to high

Fig. 5. Mean PFAS removal after hydrothermal carbonization at Phases A and B (200 °C, 17 bar, 2 h contact time) (a) and Phase C (250 °C, 36 bar, 2 h contact time) (b).

temperatures (165–300 °C) increased the concentrations of some PFAS. It should also be noted that the improved extractability of PFAS, resulting from the breakdown of the complex anaerobically digested sludge matrix during HTC, could lead to their release and contribute to the apparent increase in their concentrations after HTC [59].

Concerning the PFSAs (C4–C6), removal efficiencies ranged from $64 \pm 16\%$ for PFPeS to $100 \pm 0\%$ for PFHxS during Phases A and B, whereas in Phase C, the values ranged from $56 \pm 35\%$ for PFBS to $90 \pm 10\%$ for PFHxS. No statistically significant differences in removal were observed for these PFSAs between the phases; however, it is noteworthy that PFHxS was removed to a substantially greater extent compared to the other two PFSAs. Unexpectedly, at the temperature of 200 °C and pressure of 17 bar (Phases A and B) significantly higher removal of PFOS was observed in comparison to Phase C in which higher temperature and pressure were applied, $84 \pm 1\%$ and $39 \pm 15\%$, respectively. PFNS was completely removed (100%) during Phase C, whereas it was not detected at the inlet and outlet of the HTC reactor during Phases A and B. Hydrothermal treatment has shown to be more effective on the removal

of PFAS with carboxylate functional groups than those with sulfonate groups [14,15]. Yu et al. [60] reported degradation of 67% for PFOS at 350 °C for 80 min, while PFAS with carboxylic functional group degraded by more than 99%. Miserli et al. [14] reported complete removal (100%) of five PFCAs, including PFOA, whereas several PFSAs, including PFOS (44.5%), showed greater stability under the same experimental conditions.

PFOSA which belong to the group of perfluoroalkanesulfonamides showed partial removal ($65 \pm 4\%$) during Phase C, while it was not detected at the inlet and outlet of the reactor during Phases A and B. Regarding the new generation PFAS, Adona exhibited removal in the range 35–100% (Phase C), while during the first two Phases it was not detected. On the other hand, GenX was not removed at all.

In the literature, the exact pathways of PFAS breakdown during thermal treatment under both subcritical and supercritical water conditions remain unclear. Proposed degradation mechanisms are primarily based on the detected reaction intermediates, and several pathways have been suggested to explain PFAS transformation under these

conditions. PFAS degradation generally involves nucleophilic substitution, where hydroxide ions attack the polar head groups, forming unstable intermediates that undergo hydroxylation, decarboxylation, and defluorination, leading to stepwise chain shortening and the formation of short-chain PFAS, fluoride ions, and CO₂. Direct defluorination via C–C bond cleavage can also occur but requires higher activation energy [16,58,61]. Additionally, metal ions and mineral solids in sludge may act as catalysts, facilitating PFAS degradation [59]. Overall, PFAS removal during hydrothermal treatment proceeds through multiple parallel pathways, combining chain shortening and defluorination. Additionally, to the above, a recent study from our research team also showed that trace amounts of PFAS removed during HTC were detected in the gas phase [15], indicating that emissions to the gas phase cannot be excluded. Future studies incorporating fluoride ion measurements, total organic fluorine analysis, high-resolution non-target mass spectrometry and sampling in the gas phase are required to provide a more comprehensive understanding of PFAS fate and enable closure of the fluorine mass balance under HTC conditions.

In addition to changes in the total concentrations of most PFAS, the application of HTC also affected their distribution between dissolved and particulate phase. Specifically, a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in the proportion of PFTeDA, PFTTrDA, PFHxA, PFUdA, PFBA, and PFPeA associated with the particulate phase of the hydrochar was noticed for both experimental conditions (Fig. S5a and 5b). Additionally, the same pattern was observed for PFOS, PFOA, PFPeA and 8:2 FTS after applying temperature of 250 °C and pressure of 36 bar (Phase C). In contrast, 6:2 FTS showed an increase in the solid phase under both experimental conditions, whereas PFHpA and PFHxS exhibited enhanced partitioning to the solids at 200 °C and 17 bar.

3.7. Energy consumption of the pilot system

A three-phase energy meter was installed in the pilot system's electrical panel at the beginning of the experiments to monitor and record energy consumption associated with sludge pumping, operation of the anaerobic digester, and sludge pretreatment systems. The daily energy consumption was 11.4 ± 2.8 kWh d⁻¹ in Phase A, 19.0 ± 1.2 kWh d⁻¹ in Phase B, and 19.0 ± 3.6 kWh d⁻¹ in Phase C. The highest energy demands recorded in Phases B and C are attributed to the fact that these Phases were conducted during the winter months, when the boiler operated continuously to maintain a stable temperature in the anaerobic bioreactor. In general, heating of the anaerobic digester accounted for the largest fraction of total energy use, ranging from 46% in Phase A to 56% in Phase C (Fig. S6). Several key parameters were calculated for each technology and Experimental Phase, including the corresponding volumetric energy, specific energy input, specific energy consumption per VS destroyed, and specific energy consumption per increase of sCOD. These parameters are presented in detail in Table S10.

Regarding sludge pretreatment technologies, their contributions to overall energy consumption were 23% (4.5 ± 0.2 kWh d⁻¹) for thermal pretreatment and 5% (0.9 ± 0.1 kWh d⁻¹) for ultrasound pretreatment. The corresponding volumetric energy (E_V) values were calculated as 161 and 32 kWh m⁻³ of sludge for thermal and ultrasound pretreatment, respectively. According to the literature, E_V values in thermal sludge pretreatment are strongly influenced by sludge concentration, treatment duration, and applied temperature [22]. In the studied system, a critical factor was the time required for the temperature to reach 80 °C (approximately 1 h), before thermal pretreatment of the sludge began. A theoretical analysis of thermal sludge pretreatment (at a concentration of 150 g L⁻¹) previously estimated the energy requirements for various energy integration strategies, to both lab- and industrial-scale systems, as follows: approximately 205 kWh m⁻³ of sludge for no heat recovery, 116 kWh m⁻³ for heat recovery from the flash step, 65 kWh m⁻³ for thermal heating, and 10–15 kWh m⁻³ for combined heat and power (CHP) integration [62].

In terms of ultrasound pretreatment, the estimated E_V demand is

strongly correlated with the amount of sludge treated, the treatment duration and the scale of the system [63]. In two full-scale ultrasonic pretreatment systems, with power capacities of up to 4000 W, E_V values of 6.3 and 16 kWh m⁻³ were reported [63]. In the present study, the recorded E_V value was higher compared to those reported in the literature [63,64]. The observed difference can be attributed to the combined effect of a prolonged treatment duration (15 min), a relatively high-power capacity (900 W), and a small transducer operating volume (4.9 L). Another key parameter directly associated with electricity consumption in ultrasound pretreatment is the specific energy input (SE), which in our case was 3.5 kWh kg⁻¹ TS. A typical range of SE values is 0.28 to 4.44 kWh kg⁻¹ TS, with higher sludge concentrations generally corresponding to lower minimum SE values due to increased process efficiency [65].

Regarding the energy consumption of HTC, measurements were taken only during Phase C, showing an energy demand of 6.9 ± 0.6 kWh d⁻¹ (Fig. S7). Taking into account this value, the contribution of HTC to the total daily energy consumption of the pilot system was 28%. The estimated E_V for operating the HTC reactor (at 250 °C, 36 bar, 2 h) was 125 kWh m⁻³ (Table S10), which is comparable to other reported technologies and commercial operations summarized in a recent review, such as TerraNova Energy, which reports a total energy consumption of 118 kWh m⁻³ (115 kWh ton⁻¹) of sludge [63]. However, the energy consumption of HTC systems depends strongly on the type of sludge, as well as the operating temperature, pressure, and processing time. As expected, calculation of the specific energy consumption per VS destroyed showed that HTC requires more than double the energy (465 kWh kg⁻¹ VS_{destroyed}) compared to AD (193 kWh kg⁻¹ VS_{destroyed}) to destroy the same amount of VS (Table S10).

In the case of full-scale application of the tested technologies, the overall energy efficiency could be improved through several strategies. Heat recovery and energy integration between process units, such as using thermal energy from the HTC effluent to preheat sludge entering the AD or pretreatment stages, could substantially reduce the thermal energy demand [64]. Additionally, the use of renewable energy sources, such as solar panels for heating the AD reactor, could further reduce operational costs [66]. Finally, optimizing pretreatment conditions, such as heating-up time and power input, could reduce electricity consumption in both thermal and ultrasonic pretreatment stages.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of 27 PFAS in raw sludge showed that most were mainly found in the particulate phase. No overall PFAS removal was observed during sludge AD or sludge pretreatment; however, the distribution of some PFAS between dissolved and particulate phase slightly affected by pretreatment. The use of HTC resulted to significant overall removal of most studied PFAS, while thirteen substances were removed at a rate exceeding 80% and important differences were observed between different studied classes. For the conditions tested, PFAS removal remained largely unaffected by variations in temperature and pressure during HTC. Regarding the general performance of the system, the application of thermal pretreatment of sewage sludge at 80 °C for 1 h or the use of ultrasound pretreatment at 20 kHz and 900 W for 15 min increased significantly the concentration of sCOD in the anaerobic digester and enhanced biogas production. Energy calculations in Phase C showed that the heating of the anaerobic digester accounted for 52% of the total energy consumption, while the contribution of HTC and ultrasound pretreatment contributed by 27% and 7%, respectively.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evdokia Gkalipidou: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Asimina Koukoura:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Ioanna Savvanidou:** Investigation. **Marios G. Kostakis:** Validation, Formal analysis. **Dimitrios Triantafyllos Gerokonstantis:**

Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Petros Mastoras:** Investigation. **Georgia Gatidou:** Project administration, Methodology. **Michail S. Fountoulakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Stergios Vakalis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Olga S. Arvaniti:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Nikolaos S. Thomaidis:** Resources, Methodology. **Olga-Ioanna Kalantzi:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Athanasios S. Stasinakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2026.174358>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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